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EMERGING ROLE OF MAGNESIUM IN MODERN ANAESTHESIA, ANALGESIA, OBSTETRICS & CRITICAL CARE.**Dr. Manisha Kapdi (Associate professor of Anaesthesia, NHLM Medical college Ahmedabad Gujarat India)**

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Abstract:

Magnesium is an ancient cation but it can be used successfully as adjuvant to Local anaesthetic agent. It can be used successfully in various Surgeries like neurosurgery, cardiac surgery, as induced hypotensive agent, in FESS Surgeries, used for attenuation of pressure response to laryngoscopy & intubation, also to prevent postoperative sore throat. It can be used in critical care, & in obstetrics to prevent Eclampsia. In present article various uses of Magnesium sulfate discussed.

Keyword: MAGNESIUM, ANAESTHESIA, ANALGESIA, OBSTETRICS, CRITICAL CARE, MODERN.

Introduction

Magnesium is the second most abundant intracellular cation^{1,2} and the fourth when the extracellular medium is also considered¹. It is involved biological reactions, such as³: hormone binding to receptors, flow of trans-membrane ions, regulation of the adenylate kinase system, muscle contraction, neuronal activity, vasomotor tone, cardiac excitability, release of neurotransmitters, and calcium binding to calcium channels.

In 1906, Haulbold and Meltzer reported sensorial and motor blockades in humans after the intrathecal administration of magnesium; in 1950, magnesium was used in anesthesia, mainly to control seizures in gravidas. Currently, it has several applications in anesthesia, obstetrics, and critical care³⁻⁵. The objective of present review was to access the physiology, pharmacology, and reduction in plasma levels of magnesium, as well as some of its applications in obstetrics, anesthesia, analgesia, & critical care

PHYSIOLOGY AND PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECTS

Magnesium is an intracellular cation with multiple functions: it participates in energy metabolism, since it is a cofactor in glucose metabolism, and a cofactor of nucleic acid, protein, and fatty acid degradation enzymes^{5,6}; it regulates the flow of transmembrane ions⁵; and it mediates the activity of several enzymes^{5,7}. Magnesium is considered a natural physiologic calcium antagonist, having several regulatory mechanisms, such as^{1-3,8-11}: competitive antagonist affecting type L calcium channels, inhibition of the enzyme Ca²⁺-ATPase, and it is a cofactor for all enzymes that participate in phosphate transferances that use ATP. In high concentrations, it inhibits the enzyme Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase⁵. Magnesium is absorbed in the jejunum and ileum at a proportion of 11% to 65% of the ingested amount¹². The kidney is the main regulator of the levels of magnesium in the body, being capable of eliminating almost 100% of the filtered magnesium in case of overload⁵. Medicnot elucidated completely the mechanism of action of magnesium sulfate used therapeutically¹³. Some of the following proposa) and the amplitude of terminal endplate potential⁹.b)

Mechanism of action:

It is an antagonist of NMDA glutamate receptors^{1,2,5,10,11}; this receptor is responsible for central sensitization¹⁰. Binding of this receptor has analgesic, anticonvulsant, and sedative properties⁵.

- c) It can increase the synthesis of prostacyclins and inhibit angiotensin converting enzyme, leading to vasodilation¹¹.
- d) It decreases the release of catecholamines after sympathetic stimulus^{1,5,9,11}. It has been used in the treatment of pheochromocytoma-related hypertensive episodes during surgeries or outside the surgical environment⁵.
- e) In asthma patients, it inhibits the release of histamine and acetylcholine^{5,16}, and it potentiates the effects of beta-adrenergic agents⁵. It is indicated only in severe cases because it decreases the rate of hospitalizations and the length of stay in the intensive care unit, but it has little beneficial effects in moderate and mild cases¹⁶.

Formulation

For Intramuscular, intravenous use each ml of magnesium sulfate (heptahydrate) 500 mg, provide 4.06 meq of mgso₄ & water for injection. PH- 5.5-7. No preservative, no bacteriostatic agent added.

Molecular Formula: Mgso₄·7H₂O Molecular weight:246.67 HYPOMAGNESEMIA & CRITICAL CARE

The human body has 21 to 28 grams of magnesium⁵. It is distributed as follows: 53% in the bones, 27% in the muscles, 19% in the soft tissues, 0.3% in the red blood cells, and 0.3% in the plasma^{5,6}. Fifty-five per cent of plasma magnesium is ionized and 45% is bound to plasma proteins or broken into divalent anions, such as phosphate and sulfate⁶. Its plasma concentration ranges from 1.6 to 2.3 mg.dL⁻¹^{5,6}. Since magnesium is an abundant intracellular ion and it is present in the plasma in very low amounts, measuring its plasma levels is not adequate to evaluate real deficiency or overload⁵.

Body magnesium stores are better assessed by measuring the urinary excretion in patients without renal failure^{5,6}. Under normal circumstances, a small amount of magnesium is eliminated in the urine⁶. The urinary retention test is performed by collecting 24-hour urine after the intravenous infusion of 6 g of magnesium sulfate⁶. When more than 70% of the amount administered is recovered from the urine, the presence of deficiency is unlikely⁵, but when less than 50% is recovered from the urine, body stores are probably deficient⁶.

Hypomagnesemia is seen in 10% to 20% of hospitalized internal medicine patients⁶, and 60% of patients in Intensive Care Units (ICU)^{6,7}, 7% of admissions for ketoacidosis, 30% of admissions to the neonatal ICU, and up to 70% after coronary revascularization in adults⁵. The presence of hypo-magnesemia in the surgical ICU has been associated with increased mortality⁷.

Coronary Critical care patients

Clinical signs of hypomagnesemia are non-specific⁶, and they are associated with cardiac arrhythmia⁸, reduction in cardiac index⁸, reduction in neuromuscular excitability⁷, disorientation⁹, seizures⁹, and psychosis⁹. It is the main cause of refractory hypokalemia⁷.

Sepsis, diabetic patients

Critical patients have a tendency to develop hypomagnesemia for several reasons: deficient intake, increased losses, and re-distribution in the body⁵. The main cause of hypomagnesemia is the use of diuretics and it is seen in 50% of chronic furosemide users⁶. Other possible causes include⁵: total parenteral nutrition; pancreatitis; burns; extracorporeal circulation; use of beta-agonists, aminoglycosides, and amphotericin B; diarrhea; acute tubular necrosis; and hypoparathyroidism.

Treatment consists on correcting the underlying cause, when-ever possible, and replacement of magnesium⁵. Intestinal absorption of magnesium is erratic and the intravenous route should be preferred for therapeutic use^{5,7}. Six grams should be administered in 24 hours^{5,7} and, in critical patients, serum levels should be maintained above 2.0 mg. dL⁻¹⁷.

Obstretic Uses

Magnesium sulfate has been used in obstetrics since 1925 for prevention of seizures in eclampsia^{17,18}, with the advantage of decreasing peripheral vascular resistance without changing uterine blood flow⁵.

It has been postulated that the **anticonvulsant** property of magnesium sulfate is due to the blockade of NMDA receptors^{5,14}.

a) CNS & Neuromuscular junction effects:

Considerations on the real effects of magnesium in the treatment of eclampsia-related seizures have been made, since its effects in the neuromuscular junction can mask the real effects of magnesium in the central nervous system¹⁹. Doses used to depress the activity of the neuromuscular junction have been used in gravidas²⁰, and small alterations or even no changes on the electroencephalogram have been reported in some studies with women without eclampsia²¹, with eclampsia²², and in animal models²³. Studies with Doppler flowmetry have demonstrated cerebral vasodilation^{2,5} and reversion of cerebral vasospasm^{2,15} after the administration of magnesium.

The therapeutic serum level for the treatment of seizures ranges from 4.2 to 8.4 mg.dL⁻¹ which can be achieved by the intramuscular administration of 6 g followed by 2 g/hour; intravenous administration of 3 to 4 g (up to 1 g/min) or a combination of both routes¹⁹. Two administration schedules of magnesium are widely used: Pritchard's and Zuspan's¹⁸.

b) Pritchard's schedule

It starts with a 14-gram dose, 4 g IV and 5 g in each gluteal region¹⁸. Maintenance is achieved with 5 g every 4 hours in the gluteal region¹⁸.

c) Zuspan's schedule
Bolus 4 g IV¹⁸, followed by continuous infusion of 1 g/hour¹⁸. Elevated plasma levels are associated with adverse effects (Table I); therefore, it is necessary to observe some clinical parameters to guarantee the safety of its use¹⁷. Those parameters include: diuresis of 25 mL.h⁻¹, positive patellar reflex, respiratory rate greater than 12 bpm, and unchanged vital signs (blood pressure, heart rate, and level of consciousness)¹⁷. Magnesium decreases by 52% of the risk of seizures when compared to diazepam, and 67% when compared to phenytoin²⁴. This study increased the use of magnesium from 2% to 40% in patients with preeclampsia in the United Kingdom¹⁹. Benzodiazepines are indicated for the treatment of seizures

Table I -

Clinical Manifestations of Hypermagnesemia Serum levels in mg.dL⁻¹

Serum levels (mg.dL ⁻¹)	Symptom
5-9	Therapeutic
10-15	Areflexia
15-20	Respiratory arrest
≥ 25	Cardiac arrest

only postpartum¹⁷, in the absence of magnesium sulfate¹⁷, or when treatment with magnesium sulfate has failed².

Further studies on this area will focus on aquaporin 4¹⁹, a water channel-bound protein found in the final portion of astrocyte axon, whose levels are increased in cerebral edema¹⁹. Magnetic resonance imaging studies have documented cerebral edema of the white matter of the posterior region of the brain eclampsia patients²⁵. This change has also been documented in animal models of eclampsia²⁵. The expression of aquaporin

4 is increased in pregnancy²⁶, and the use of magnesium sulfate decreases cerebral expression of this protein, which can attenuate cerebral edema in eclampsia patients²⁷.

Magnesium has been used as the standard drug for tocolysis during treatment of premature labor, and other drugs have been compared to it²⁸. The mechanism of action has not been completely elucidated, but it seems to be secondary to calcium antagonism by competing for

the binding site of this ion²⁸. The loading dose for tocolysis ranges from 4 to 6 g intravenous over 15 to 30 minutes, followed by maintenance with 2 to 6 g IV/hour²⁸. Several patients treated with magnesium developed minor adverse reactions, such as: feeling hot, scotomata, nausea, vomiting, blurred or double vision, and lethargy^{5,28}. Adverse effects can be reverted by the intravenous administration of 1 g of calcium gluconate⁵.

ANESTHESIA & CRITICAL CARE CONSIDERATIONS:

The indications of magnesium sulfate in anesthesia have been increasing over the years to include situations out of the gynecological field⁵. It has analgesic and sedative properties with potential neuro- and cardioprotective effects, although it is not known the mechanisms of those actions^{5,29}.

Myocardial & cerebral Ischemia acute myocardial infarction (AMI), 80% of the patients develop hypomagnesemia in the first 48 hours, probably secondary to the high serum levels of catecholamines⁶. Magnesium deficiency leads to cell depolarization and promotes tachycardia⁶. Two studies using magnesium in patients with AMI, LIMIT 2 and ISIS 4, showed antagonistic mortality results⁵. Only LIMIT 2 showed a reduction in mortality, but magnesium was used before spontaneous or pharmacologic recovery of the occluded vessel⁵. The prophylactic use to prevent hypomagnesemia during extracorporeal circulation is controversial, although reduction in the incidence of ventricular tachycardia and atrial fibrillation has been shown⁵.

Neuronal ischemia leads to the outflow of ATP from the cell and inflow of calcium, which triggers the release of toxic metabolites, culminating with cell death⁵. Blockade of glutamate NMDA receptors inhibits the cellular inflow of calcium and contributes for neuronal protection^{3,29-31}. Other probable actions for cerebral protection include: reduction in the presynaptic release of excitatory neurotransmitters³², blockade of calcium channels^{32,33}, suppression of anoxic depolarization³², antioxidant effects^{31,32}, an increase in cerebral blood flow^{29,30,32,33}. Besides, cellular energy preservation is also seen, since magnesium is bound to ATP in the cytosol.

Two studies demonstrated antagonistic results in patients with cerebral ischemia, IMAGE and FAST-MAG³². A 90 mg.kg⁻¹ dose reduced infarction volume after middle cerebral artery embolus by 48% when administered in the first six hours³². It is possible that the doses used in the IMAGE study have not been enough to cause an increase in the concentration of magnesium in cerebral cells¹⁵.

Attenuation of stress response to intubation:

Magnesium has been used to attenuate the cardiovascular response to tracheal intubation⁵. This effect is, probably, secondary to a reduction in the release of catecholamines after sympathetic stimulation^{1,3,5,11,34,35}. A 40 mg.kg⁻¹ dose has shown similar efficacy to that of 10 µg.kg⁻¹ of alfentanil as well as greater effectiveness than 1.5 mg.kg⁻¹ of lidocaine⁵. It is a complementary drug in the treatment of hypertensive episodes during the surgical treatment of pheochromocytoma, since it inhibits the release of catecholamines from the adrenal glands⁵.

Effects on Neuromuscular junction & interaction with Relaxants:

Magnesium inhibits the release of acetylcholine in the neuromuscular junction and behaves as a neuromuscular relaxant, potentiating the effects of non-depolarizing neuromuscular blockers⁵. A 40 mg.kg⁻¹ dose of magnesium reduces the ED₅₀ of vecuronium by 25%⁵. When magnesium is administered before induction, it prevents succinylcholine-induced increase in potassium levels^{9,36}. This drug limits muscular fasciculation, but does not interfere with the time of recovery of succinylcholine³⁶.

The analgesic potential of magnesium is partially secondary to the blockade of NMDA receptors, but also to a reduction in the release of catecholamines¹¹. The potential to reduce the MAC of volatile anesthetics has been confirmed in laboratorial studies with rat models^{1,5,37}, and it can be as high as 60%¹. Schutz-Stubner et al.³ demonstrated a reduction in the need of remifentanyl and fentanyl when one intravenous dose of 50 mg.kg⁻¹ of magnesium was used in humans. Collateral effects were not observed with this dose³.

Magnesium as adjuvant to local anaesthetic agent in spinal, Epidural ,caudal anaesthesia and peripheral nerve blockages.

Magnesium is successful adjuvant to LA by its NMDA antagonism effect, it prolongs sensorimotor blockage.

A) adjuvant to LA in spinal anaesthesia

Sarika Sarkar et al. use different doses of MgSO₄ as adjuvant to bupivacaine & compare with Fentanyl in spinal anaesthesia & concluded that MgSO₄ is good adjuvant to bupivacaine in spinal anaesthesia and improves sensorimotor blockage characteristics in spinal anaesthesia & dose dependably, prolonged postoperative analgesia (39). Satish Kumar Chaudhary et al. use different doses of MgSO₄ in spinal anaesthesia and concluded that MgSO₄ improves spinal bupivacaine effects. (40)

B) Adjuvant in Epidural anaesthesia

Sonali Banwait, Sujata Sharma have compared 75 mg of MgSO₄ & 1 mcg/kg of Fentanyl as adjuvant to LA & showed that epidural magnesium decreases Verbal rating scale, prolongs duration of Analgesia. (41)

Tanmay Ghatak et al. evaluated 50 mg MgSO₄/ 150 mcg clonidine as an adjuvant to epidural Bupivacaine & concluded that MgSO₄ group showed no shivering, Rapid onset, without adverse effects. (42)

C) MgSO₄ as adjuvant to LA in paediatric caudal Anaesthesia

Hegar Reface et al. compare 1 mcg/ Kg of Dexmedetomidine/ 50 mg MgSO₄ and showed that both adjuvants improve sensorimotor blockage characteristics, post-op Analgesia of LA. (43)

D) MgSO₄ in Peripheral nerve blockage

James MF shown mechanism of action of MgSO₄ in Peripheral nerve blockage as it interferes with release of neurotransmitter in synaptic cleft & potentiates LA action. (44,45)

Elshama HA et al. use MgSO₄ in femoral nerve blockage & concluded that MgSO₄ potentiates action of LA. (46)

Hasan et al. had used MgSO₄ in thoracic paravertebral block with bupivacaine for analgesia in MRM surgery & concluded effective role of MgSO₄ in block. (47)

Goyal P had used MgSO₄ in brachial plexus blockage & shown analgesic properties of MgSO₄. (48)

Topical magnesium sulfate to prevent postoperative sore throat.(POST)

Narinder Singh et al. proved that topical MgSO₄ prevents POST effectively. (49)

Sunil Rajan, George Malayil et al. showed ketamine/ MgSO₄ nebulization can attenuate POST. (50)

Magnesium in cardiac Anaesthesia

Magnesium is very useful for maintenance fluid infusion & for prevention of arrhythmias.

Mansoor Jannati et al. use 1.5-2 gr of MgSO₄ in cardiovascular surgery in IV/ oral formulation & concluded that decrease in prevalence of arrhythmia by cost-effective method. (51)

Robie Soliman have given 15mg/kg/ hr of magnesium infusion 20 min before induction & found decrease in Tropornin I ,CK-MB level,lower ECG changes, increase E/A peak ratio,Enddiastolic volume, Cardiac index.there was decrease in Heart rate,mean Pulmonary artery Pressure Pulmonary vascular Resistance, pharmacological & Mechanical support in group magnesium than in control group.(52)

A Roscoac ,A .Ahmed etal done survey of perioperative use of Mgso4 in cardiovascular surgery in Uk & concluded that Mgso4 is advantageous in cardiac surgery.(53)

Magnesium in Neuroanaesthesia

Magnesium is used successfully as adjuvant to general anaesthesia for resection of tumors.

Charu Mahajan etal have given lignocaine 1.5-2 mg/ kg bolus following 2 mg/ kg/ hour in lignocaine group

In Mgso4 group Mgso4 50 mg/ kg bolus following by 25 mg/ kg/ hour as.adjuvant in supratentorial resection of tumor,& access post-op Analgesia, opioid requirements ,VAS,S100 B levels.They have found decrease VAS, fentanyl consumption in lignocaine & Mgso4 group then in saline group.but 24 hr S100 B level was decrease in Mgso4 group which suggests neuroprotective Effects of Mgso4.S100B is calcium binding protein having Alpha& beta subunits.Beta units present in glial& Schwan cells.Increase level of it in brain injury & poor outcome.so decrease level of it suggests

Enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS)in Mgso4 group.(54)

Magnesium for induce hypotension

Magnesium causes induced hypotension & very useful to prevent blood loss. N M Elsgarnouby use Magnesium infusion for FESS surgery to prevent blood loss.They used 40 mg/ kg bolus following 15 mg/ kg/ hr.It decrease blood loss, MAP,HR,Anaesthetic requirements of fentanyl, Vecuronium,sevoflurane.They have access blood loss by Boezaart score.(55)

SaudersGM,Sim Km, used Magnesium as hypotensive agent in oral& faciomaxillary Surgery . They used 40 gr/ hr to maintain 55+/-5 mm of Hg then5 gr/ hr until 30 min before end of surgery.(56)

Mgso4 for attenuation of Pressure response in laproscopy surgery

Shruti Kamble etal compare Mgso4 with clonidine for attenuation of Pressure response to pnemoperitonium in the laproscopy surgery & concluded that mgso4 successfully attenuate pressure response(57) **Mgso4 as adjuvant in pheochromocytoma**

Pits Miller etal use mgso4 successfully to control blood pressure in recetion of pheochromocytoma.(58)

In nutshell,Magnesium sulfate has been used in obstetrics with good results inhibiting of premature labor and in the treatment of eclampsia-related seizures. This drug is potentially analgesic and sedative and it could be used as adjuvant during general anesthesia, reducing the blood pressure response to tracheal intubation and decreasing the need of anesthetic agents.It could be safely used as adjuvant to local anaesthetic agent in spinal, epidural,caudal, Anaesthesia, various peripheral blockages.It is used in cardiac Anaesthesia since recently it is started to be used in various neurosurgery, laproscopic surgery,for induce hypotension,& nebulization of it prevents postoperative sore throat,haorseness of voice following endotracheal intubation.so it is a single costeffective drug with multiple uses.

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